

Chemistry of Thorium. Part III. Substitution Reactions of Thorium(IV) Chloride with Some Organic Acids

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Substitution reactions of ThCl_4 with several simple and substituted carboxylic acids have been carried out by heating an excess of the acid with ThCl_4 . The properties of the products obtained have been studied and their structures discussed.

Several basic and normal and anhydrous and hydrated organic salts of thorium are known¹. In recent years several organic acids have been used either to study the formation of complex compounds of thorium and their utility in analytical chemistry or for its separation from rare-earths.

Jantsh and Urbach² prepared anhydrous acetate and chloro and normal benzoates of thorium by heating anhydrous ThCl_4 with respective acid in different organic media till the evolution of HCl (gas) had ceased. With methyl salicylate, $\text{ThCl}_4 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OHCOOCH}_3$ was obtained in warm ether, but when anhydrous reactants were heated in different high boiling organic solvents, mono-, di-, and tri-substitution products were obtained after the evolution of HCl (gas) had ceased, but elimination of the fourth chlorine atom was not possible even at the boiling temperature of the ester. Young³ prepared the compound $\text{ThCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$.

A general survey of the literature shows that when reactions are carried out in water, only basic salts are obtained in majority of the cases. The present investigation was undertaken with a view to preparing the normal salts of thorium by the interaction of ThCl_4 and some organic acids in ether.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anhydrous ThCl_4 was prepared by the method of Dean and Chandler⁴ and extracted with anhydrous ether. The other chemicals used were of B.D.H. or Merck's 'E.P.' quality. The acids were recrystallised and dehydrated before use.

General Method of Preparation

In all the cases, an excess of an ethereal suspension of the acid was added to a solution of ThCl_4 in ether in a conical flask fitted with drying tubes and the mixture heated at 55-60° for about an hour and then the temperature slowly raised till it reached 15-25° above

1. Mellor, "A Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. VII, 1927.
2. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1919, 2, 490.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 29.
4. *Nuclear Sci. & Eng.*, 1957, 2, 57.

TABLE I

Acids.	Colour.	% Thorium.		% Chlorine.		% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		Probable formula.
		Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.	
Lauric	White	22.00	22.38	Nil	Nil	56.30	56.02	9.18	8.95	Th(C ₁₁ H ₂₃ COO) ₄
Myristic	"	20.67	20.36	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th(C ₁₃ H ₂₇ COO) ₄
Palmitic	"	18.46	18.54	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th(C ₁₅ H ₃₁ COO) ₄
Stearic	"	17.38	17.02	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th(C ₁₇ H ₃₅ COO) ₄
Succinic	"	50.36	50.61	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \\ \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \end{array} \right\}_2$
Adipic	"	44.00	44.03	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO} \\ \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO} \end{array} \right\}_2$
Sebacic	"	30.14	30.72	"	"	38.31	37.07	5.20	5.06	Th[(CH ₂) ₈ (COO)] ₂
Phthalic	Dirty white	40.87	41.44	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th[C ₆ H ₄ (COO)] ₂
Malic	White	40.26	49.65	7.51	7.62	"	"	"	"	Th ₂ Cl ₂ $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CH}_2\text{COO} \\ \text{CHOHCOO} \end{array} \right\}_3$
Salicylic	"	33.07	34.20	5.06	5.23	37.46	37.13	2.50	2.21	ThCl(C ₆ H ₄ OHCOO) ₂
Tartaric	Dirty brown	42.36	43.65	Nil	Nil	"	"	"	"	Th $\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{CHOHCOO} \\ \text{CHOHCOO} \end{array} \right\}_2$
Citric	Brown	46.73	47.94	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th ₃ (C ₆ H ₇ O ₇) ₄
Crotonic	White	40.03	40.57	"	"	33.74	33.50	3.68	3.40	Th(CH ₃ CH:CHCOO) ₄
Cinnamic	"	28.57	28.30	"	"	"	"	"	"	Th(C ₉ H ₇ CH:CHCOO) ₄

the melting point of the acid. When the evolution of HCl (gas) had ceased, the product was cooled, extracted with ether, and filtered. It was washed free of the reactants, dried in vacuum over fused calcium chloride, and analysed. The products obtained with citric and tartaric acids on cooling were extracted with ether which on evaporation gave hygroscopic, coloured, and crystalline compounds.

Thorium was estimated as ThO_2 by charring a weighed quantity of the substance with H_2SO_4 (conc.) followed by its oxidation with fuming nitric acid and precipitating $\text{Th}_2(\text{OH})_4$ by adding an excess of NH_4OH . It was filtered, washed, dried, ignited, and weighed as ThO_2 . Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method. In a few cases carbon and hydrogen were estimated by the combustion method and the percentage of organic matter calculated. In the rest it was found by difference.

General Properties.—All the compounds except those obtained with citric and tartaric acids are coloured, semicrystalline, stable in air, slightly soluble in ether and ethanol but insoluble in benzene, chloroform, and carbon tetrachloride. The compounds obtained with citric and tartaric acids are crystalline, hygroscopic, and highly soluble in ether and ethanol but insoluble in inert organic solvents. Compounds are, however, not pure. Normal salts were obtained in all the cases except in the cases of salicylic and malic acids which gave rise to the formation of chloro-salts. Both, the normal and chloro salts, are hydrolysed by boiling water and caustic alkali solution, the latter more readily. Derivatives of simple carboxylic acids are more stable than those of substituted ones.

DISCUSSION

One molecule of ThCl_4 reacts with four molecules of monobasic and two of dicarboxylic acids whereas three molecules of ThCl_4 require four molecules of a tricarboxylic acid for the formation of normal salts. Only H atom of $-\text{COOH}$ group is affected but not that of $-\text{OH}$ group, which has been confirmed as the compound obtained with salicylic acid, on treatment with neutral FeCl_3 solution, developed a violet coloration. The mode of formation and the solubility of these salts in organic solvents suggest their covalent structure.

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